

NUMERICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF THE KNOCK-DOWN FACTOR ON UNSTIFFENED CYLINDRICAL SHELLS WITH INITIAL GEOMETRIC IMPERFECTIONS

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ABSTRACT

With the evolution of composite materials and moreover of the manufacturing process of large composite structures, a new window of possibilities is opened from the optimization point of view. Currently, one has great materials and reliable manufacturing processes than can be used for extremely optimized structures. The problem is that even nowadays some calculation processes make use of design guidelines based on data from 50 years ago, which limits the optimization process due to outdated allowables and process tolerances, increasing the final cost of the structure and putting on the edge the reliability of the entire design process.

Currently, imperfection sensitive shell structures prone to buckling are designed according to the NASA SP-8007 guideline, dating from 1968, using its conservative lower bound curve. In this guideline the structural behaviour of composite materials is not appropriately considered, since the imperfection sensitivity and the buckling load of shells made of such materials depend among other things on the lay-up design as well.

In this context, a numerical investigation about the different methodologies to characterize the behaviour of imperfection sensitive composite structures subjected to compressive loads up to buckling is presented. A benchmark test is developed using a 500 mm diameter unstiffened composite cylindrical shell. A series of non-linear analyses considering geometric and thickness imperfection, obtained from real measurements, are carried-out to characterize the knock-down factor of the benchmark test. The effect of each type of imperfection on the knock-down factor is compared against the experimental results.

1 INTRODUCTION

All current design scenarios [1,2] for thin-walled composite unstiffened cylindrical structures for aeronautics have the property that when a perfect realization of the structure undergoes bifurcation the load carrying capacity dramatically decreases [3], and the bifurcation load is the (local) maximum load that can be supported by structure. This is mainly by small imperfections [4], arising from various sources [5,6] usually have an appreciable effect on the maximum load that such structures can support [3]. However, the theoretical predictions of geometrically perfect structures often considerably over predict the buckling loads of inherently imperfect real structures. Searching for “worst” [7] our most affecting load carrying capacity imperfections [4] may involve both extensive experimental work [3]

our probabilistic [8] and stochastic [9] approach applied for numerical extrapolation. A more realistic classification by manufacturing signatures [6] is requiring dedicated inputs from the manufacturers of those components, which not necessary would be granted. Even though it is reasonably well understood [2,10] how the shell geometry affects the imperfection sensitivity of axially compressed cylindrical shells however, the effects of shell lay-up, stiffener placement [10], boundary conditions [2] and dynamics [11] on the imperfection sensitivity is relatively unknown. Investigations on robustness [12] suggested that even a single perturbation introduction (Single Perturbation Load Approach) may cause dramatic decrease in load carrying capacity, which by any means are still considerably less conservative [13,14] as traditional knock down factor (KDF) [2]. As a next step a more robust fast design procedure is required for preliminary design phase as semi analytical [15] our approximation based [16] ones. On other hand a promising results has been obtained for estimation of actual load carrying capacity on laboratory scale structures with measured geometrical imperfection by means of non-destructive testing and Vibration correlation technique [17,18].

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Material characterization

Material characterization of IM7/8552 carbon fiber pre-preg material used for the manufacturing of test specimens done by means of structural testing of the coupon specimens as well as of the identification of the material properties based on vibration experiments and optimization techniques. Vibration experiments supported by the ultrasonic thickness measurements are performed for the same plates used later for coupon specimen manufacturing. This approach can be used for material characterization of realized structure (cylindrical shell), which due to manufacturing nature can have different material properties compared to flat plate properties.

Standard coupon test campaign was carried out for strain gauge-equipped coupon specimens cut from control flat plates manufactured employing the same technology used for cylindrical shell manufacturing. Additionally, clip-on extensometer and DIC system were used where applicable for comparison reasons. Specimen failures observed in coupon tests were within test zone for all specimens. No tab delamination, nor unusual strain gauge separations were observed. The most accurate values obtained by employing strain gauges, other two strain measurement methods, as well as NDT identification, can be used for fast proof of known material properties. Some limitation related to the DIC system alignment about the specimen surface or some unknown degree of slippage of clip-on extensometer can be the reason for the reduced accuracy. The final comparison of obtained material properties presented in Table 1, where current results were compared to the literature [1,18-21]

Table 1. Material properties for IM7/8552

	COCOMAT		ESA study		Hexcel	DESICOS (RTU)		NDT* (RTU)	
	Mean value	Standard deviation	Mean value	Standard deviation	Mean value	Mean value	Standard deviation	Mean value	Standard deviation
Stiffness	(GPa)	(%)	(GPa)	(%)	(GPa)	(GPa)	(%)	(GPa)	(%)
E_1^t	164.1	3.1	175.3	1.4	164	171.5	2.6	156.9	8.2
E_1^c	142.5	1.7	157.4	2.4	150	150.2	4.6		
E_2^t	8.7	3.9	8.6	2.9	12	8.9	4.2	10.4	4.11
E_2^c	9.7	4.9	10.1	4.1	-	9.4	10.9		
G_{12}	5.1	13.6	5.3	1.1	-	5.1	7.8	5.26	10.79
ν_{12}^t	0.28	13.5	-	-	-	0.32	13.0		
Strength	(MPa)	(%)	(MPa)	(%)	(MPa)	(MPa)	(%)		
R_1^t	1741	11.9	2440	3.6	2724	2300	13.8		
R_1^c	855	9.0	1332	7.2	1690	857	10.1		
R_2^t	29	18.1	42	26.5	64	40	20.4		
R_2^c	283	5.1	269	6.0	-	203	3.9		
R_{12}	98	17.5	129	0.8	120	-	-		
$R_{12}^{0.2}$	-	-	-	-	-	51	8.4		

NDT* identified values most likely are flexural values due to flexural nature of used vibration experiments

Note that current results were obtained for IM7/8552 cured out-of-autoclave technique, this can be the reason for slightly lower strength values obtained, but otherwise there is good correlation in comparison to the different studies. Realized ply thickness $t=0.1308$ mm obtained as average thickness of all 12 ply thickness specimens including $\pm 45^\circ$ shear specimens, is in good agreement with HEXCEL data for nominal cured ply thickness 8552/35%/134 [4] $t=0.131$ mm.

2.2 Manufacturing of test specimens

Unstiffened composite shells of $D=300$ mm and $D=500$ mm were manufactured by employing single part steel mandrels, designed for manufacturing of cylindrical shells made of pre-preg systems with high temperature curing (up to 2000C). Thermal expansion of the steel mandrel provides simple shell removing when cured and cooled down to room temperature.

Shells were manufactured from unidirectional IM7/8552 pre-preg 300 mm width tape of nominal ply thickness $t=0.125$ mm. Pre-preg tape was manually cut to desired pieces and manually stacked on mandrel, see Fig.1. No intermediate vacuum bagging for the whole lay-up was performed, since the larger ply count for test shells was 4 plies. Final debulk was carried out with perforated release ply and breather under full vacuum (-0.8 bar). Shells are oven cured under full vacuum for 6 hours. Figure 2 shows curing diagram in comparison of manufacturer specified. Temperature of the mandrel surface was recorded by two thermocouples attached to mandrel internal surface (see diagram Top TC and Mid TC).

Figure 1. Lay-up formation on steel mandrel

Figure 2. Curing cycle for composite shells.

Cured shells were precision cut to desired shell length on rotating mandrel with diamond saw. Shell edges were casted in 20 mm thick resin-sand mixture to form load distributing ring (outside ring) representing clamped boundary conditions, Fig. 3. Note, boundary conditions for experimental tests incorporates internal metallic ring (aluminium) inserted before test.

Figure 3. Casted edges of the D=500 mm composite shells.

3 IMPERFECTION MEASUREMENTS

3.1 Ultrasound thickness measurement

Ultrasound inspection of the shells was carried out on modified Hilgus USPC 3010 HF equipment, for quality control and thickness measurement reasons. Obtained bitmap files (rotated 900 CCW and vertically flipped to be aligned to shell orientation for representative reasons only) with the corresponding thickness histogram are shown in Fig. 4. Such data can be used for thickness imperfection implementation in finite element model analyses. For the implementation into the FE analyses an in-house developed software [22] was used to handle the bitmap files (rotate and flip to align, as well as to convert bitmap file to digital R , θ , z , t_i file text format).

Figure 4. An example of the thickness measurement bitmap and corresponding thickness histogram (R15 shell)

3.2 Initial geometric imperfection measurements

Initial geometrical imperfection measurements for all composite shells (R15 – R28) was carried out by photogrammetry method, additionally Exascan external laser scan and internal laser scanner (developed in RTU) was performed for R15 and R16 shells.

Figure 5 shows unfiltered imperfection pattern for R16 shell, captured by internal laser scanner and converted by set of DESICOS related Python scripts [22] to thet_z_imp format file and plotted as open plot graph. Measured imperfection amplitude to thickness ratio $a/t=1.15$. Figure xx, shows unfiltered imperfection pattern for R16 shell, captured by by Exascan laser scanner, converted to x,y,z format by Autodesk Memento project and MeshLab software and converted by set of DESICOS related Python scripts to thet_z_imp format file and plotted as open plot graph.

Figure 6, shows filtered imperfection pattern for R16 shell, captured by photogrammetry, processed to 3D object by Autodesk Recap3600 and converted to x,y,z format by Autodesk Memento project and MeshLab software, finally converted by set of DESICOS related Python scripts to thet_z_imp format file and plotted as open plot graph.

Figure 5 . R16 internal laser scan

Figure 6. R16 Exascan laser scanner

Figure 7. R16 Photogrammetry based imperfections

Comparison of the measured geometrical imperfections between different shells was considered as maximum measured imperfection amplitude to thickness ratio (a/t), results are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Comparison of the measured a/t ratios.

#	Id	Layup	Thickness t [mm] / ply thickness	Imperfections ratio a/t		
				Int. laser	Exascan laser	Photo
1	R15	[24/-24/41/-41]	0.5232 / 0.1308	1.07	1.35	1.46
2	R16	[24/-24/41/-41]	0.5232 / 0.1308	0.83	0.98	0.97
3	R17	[0/45]	0.2616 / 0.1308			2.43
4	R18	[0/45]	0.2616 / 0.1308			2.33
5	R19	[0/60/-60]	0.3924 / 0.1308			1.74
6	R20	[0/60/-60]	0.3924 / 0.1308			1.17
7	R21	[0/60/-60]	0.3924 / 0.1308			0.66
8	R22	[0/45/-45]	0.3924 / 0.1308			1.39
9	R23	[0/45/-45]	0.3924 / 0.1308			1.67
10	R24	[0/45/-45]	0.3924 / 0.1308			1.84
11	R25	[24/-24/41/-41]	0.5232 / 0.1308			0.79
12	R26	[24/-24/41/-41]	0.5232 / 0.1308			0.91
13	R27	[24/-24/41/-41]	0.5232 / 0.1308			0.96
14	R28	[24/-24/41/-41]	0.5232 / 0.1308			0.67

5 NUMERICAL PREDICTIONS

Numerical predictions based on KDF factors obtained by: SPLA analyses carried out for perfect geometry shell and NASA SP8007 guidelines. Both KDF applicable for linear buckling (eigenbuckling) value obtained for corresponding model.

Numerical analyses were carried out as non-linear (Newton-Raphson large deformation solver) analyses under displacement control, with artificial stabilization (damping factor stabilization ABAQUS/Standard). Numerical model represents finite element model composed of S8R5 shell elements used for shell structure, maintaining 12 x 12 mm mesh aspect ratio, Fig. 8. Single perturbation load approach (SPLA) analyses were performed, considering that lateral perturbation load applied before axial compression loading and remain constant during axial loading. SPLA applied on the $x=0$ and $1/2H$ of the shell. P_{load} values were considered as: 0.1,1,2,3,5,7,9,11,13,15 N.

Linear buckling analyses were carried out along with SPLA, as a reference value for KDF calculation.

Figure 8. Finite element model.

Bottom edge of the shell was considered clamped ($U_X=U_Y=U_Z=ROT_X=ROT_Y=ROT_Z=0$). Upper edge considered clamped ($U_X=U_Y=ROT_X=ROT_Y=ROT_Z=0$), except U_Z direction. Coupled set U_Z applied for the bottom edge nodes for load extraction from single pilot node reaction force. Loading was considered as displacement controlled and applied on the upper edge coupled set pilot node. Typical behavior of the shell with applied SPLA shown on Fig. 9 and corresponding KDF curve, Fig. 10.

Figure 9. SPLA applied for R15 perfect shell.

Figure 10. KDF curve obtained for R15 perfect shell.

Numerical predictions summarised in table 3. of the design load employing the NASA SP8007 guideline KDF produce conservative values when compared to SPLA approach. SPLA approach produce reasonable KDF values for shells with imperfection values about $a/t \leq 1$ (R15, R16, R25, R26, R28). Experimental results for shells (R17 –R28) were preliminary with different actual boundary conditions, compared to R15 and R16. Preliminary non-linear FEM analyses with geometric and thickness imperfections carried out for R15 and R16 shells showed predicted values from 22.6 to 33.9 kN depending on measured imperfections used. In addition, internal laser scan of geometrical imperfections should be performed for shells R17 – R28 to proof that photogrammetry based imperfections are correct.

Table 3. Comparison of the obtained numerical simulations and experimental results

#	Id	Layup	Thickness t [mm] / ply thickness	Imperfections ratio a/t			LB kN	NASA SP8007 kN (KDF)	SPLA kN (KDF)	Non- linear (perf) kN	Experime ntal kN	Exp vs.	Exp vs.
				Int. Las	Exa las	Photo						NASA KDF	SPLA Tendency
1	R15	[24/-24/41/-41]	0.5232 / 0.1308	1.07	1.35	1.46	39.00	13 (0.33)	22 (0.59)	39.00	25.38	↑	↑
2	R16	[24/-24/41/-41]	0.5232 / 0.1308	0.83	0.98	0.97	39.00	13 (0.33)	22 (0.59)	39.00	25.64	↑	↑
3	R17	[0/45]	0.2616 / 0.1308			2.43	4.26	1.3 (0.3)	3.68 (0.86)	4.36	1.60	↑	↓
4	R18	[0/45]	0.2616 / 0.1308			2.33	4.26	1.3 (0.3)	3.68 (0.86)	4.36	2.44	↑	↓
5	R19	[0/60/-60]	0.3924 / 0.1308			1.74	13.20	4.8 (0.37)	10.2 (0.77)	13.66	6.22	↑	↓
6	R20	[0/60/-60]	0.3924 / 0.1308			1.17	13.20	4.8 (0.37)	10.2 (0.77)	13.66	6.34	↑	↓
7	R21	[0/60/-60]	0.3924 / 0.1308			0.66	13.20	4.8 (0.37)	10.2 (0.77)	13.66	7.28	↑	↓
8	R22	[0/45/-45]	0.3924 / 0.1308			1.39	16.22	5.9 (0.36)	10.88 (0.67)	17.26	8.71	↑	↓
9	R23	[0/45/-45]	0.3924 / 0.1308			1.67	16.22	5.9 (0.36)	10.88 (0.67)	17.26	8.50	↑	↓
10	R24	[0/45/-45]	0.3924 / 0.1308			1.84	16.22	5.9 (0.36)	10.88 (0.67)	17.26	9.63	↑	↓
11	R25	[24/-24/41/-41]	0.5232 / 0.1308			0.79	41.27	17.0 (0.41)	24.25 (0.67)	39.48	28.96	↑	↑
12	R26	[24/-24/41/-41]	0.5232 / 0.1308			0.91	41.27	17.0 (0.41)	24.25 (0.67)	39.48	26.85	↑	↑
13	R27	[24/-24/41/-41]	0.5232 / 0.1308			0.96	41.27	17.0 (0.41)	24.25 (0.67)	39.48	21.10	↑	↓
14	R28	[24/-24/41/-41]	0.5232 / 0.1308			0.67	41.27	17.0 (0.41)	24.25 (0.67)	39.48	25.47	↑	↑

7 CONCLUSIONS

The paper highlight some of the experimental results for unstiffened composite shells under axial loading compression and tendency that traditional knock down factor approach gives too conservative buckling load estimation. An experimental study involve several approaches for geometrical imperfection measurements, which has been integrated in FEM and exploited for numerical characterisation. It has been concluded that for reliable experimental results one should consider to cast directly shells into testing frame thus avoiding onset of boundary imperfections.

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